

Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Students in North-Central Nigeria

Lawal, Fatima¹

lawalfatima36@gmail.com

07035282637

Okunloye, Rotimi Williams²

okunloyerw@unilorin.edu.ng

08035651211

Jekayinfa, Alice A.²

jekayinfaaa@unilorin.edu.ng

08033893206

¹Department of Arts and Social Science Education, Faculty of Education, Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria

²Department of Social Science Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin – Nigeria

Abstract

The main objective of the study was to examine the Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity (PI) and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria. Correlational Survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consists of all NCE Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. A sample of 750 (Male, 345 and Female, 405) students were selected from the target population using simple random sampling technique. Two research instruments were used for the study: namely, “The Integrity Scale” and the researcher-designed “Citizenship Education Performance Test”-CEPT with reliability coefficients of 0.76 and 0.82 respectively. Data were analyzed using percentages and multiple regression statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that there was a significant relationship between PI and performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies NCE students in North-central, Nigeria. The study concludes that PI has significant correlation with performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies NCE students in North-central, Nigeria. The study recommended that PI should be promoted through value education workshops and seminars among students.

Keywords: Personal Integrity, Performance, Citizenship Education, Students

Introduction

Nations of the world in general and the Nigerian nation in particular deem it fit to seek for men of great character, conscience and integrity when there is need for certain public or political positions to be occupied. It is however saddening at times when people are finally appointed or elected into such esteemed positions of authority, when statements such as “square pegs in round holes” and “round pegs in square holes” begin to suffice. In addition, some Nigerians consider government properties as general or free-for-all properties that do not need to be protected or properly maintained for the good of the populace. This can be classified as one of the reasons why some Nigerians consider national treasures as “national cake” which is to be scrambled for by all and sundry. Based on the aforementioned submissions, an inquisitive mind may begin to wonder if these and many more, are some of the reasons for the continued call by both individuals, civic society groups as well as government for the promotion of sound values and attitudes such as honesty, hard-work, integrity, patriotism and democratic principles in the educational system in part and in the nation as a whole. It is imperative for these issues to be timely nipped in the bud.

Nigeria has a country is plagued with a range of social, cultural, economic, educational and political problems which pervades all sectors and aspects of national life from technocrats to politicians. The deficiencies of well-versed and participating citizenship are major causes of these problems. It was with regard to the foregoing that the Nigeria Academy of Education in Ajose, (2001) made the submission that, there is a pressing necessity to examine the impact of citizenship education on the Nigerian society, because citizenship education is an indispensable subject that was designed especially in both content and function to produce healthy, good and active citizens. In this context, a good citizen is perceived as patriotic, disciplined, responsible and meticulous as well as ethically thorough with affection for his/her state. For example, Akpan (2001) and Edozie (2009), reported that the absence of an informed and participatory citizenship is a major factor responsible for a

number of vices bedeviling the Nigerian society. This may indicate that the practice and exhibition of salient features of good and effective citizenship education for the advancement of the coveted humane society is yet to be achieved.

In recognizing and realizing the importance and benefits of Citizenship Education, the Nigerian government has deemed it necessary to key into the educational sector as an indispensable tool in an effort at national growth and development. According to the National Policy on Education (2013), the goals of tertiary education shall include, among others, contribution to national development through high level relevant manpower while developing and inculcating proper values for the survival of individual and society. It means that education at the tertiary level is expected to inculcate in its recipients appropriate values (such as hard-work, honesty, patriotism, integrity, dignity of labour and loyalty among many others), which will equip graduates for a smooth personal transition from school-life to life outside school. These goals are expected to be pursued through teaching, research and development as well as through the generation and dissemination of knowledge. Furthermore, teacher education, both at the NCE and degree levels, shall continue to expand to cater for societal needs and changes in methodology and curriculum (NPE, 2013).

Citizenship Education as a concept and as a course of study aims at grooming members of the society with the right values, skills and morals which are vital to make them effective citizens and contribute positively to the development of their society. Citizenship Education furnishes learners with the pre-requisite academic facts and talents that enable them to understand their rights as well as civic duties and responsibilities that will improve the well-being of the people in the society. Citizenship Education as a course of study, according to Oluniyi (2011) aims at developing young people to become responsible citizens, who are familiar with their fundamental rights and responsibilities and can exhibit dynamic participatory roles in the society. The course should educate students on how they can be politically cultured while using real life situations and experiences.

Citizenship Education is designed to reveal itself as a necessity of life to individuals as well as Social Studies students because ultimately it liberates humans (Blooms, 2004; Suarez-Oroozoo, 2004). It displays education as a tool for pulling societies out of poverty, providing requisite information to all cadres of leadership and for promoting health and social growth, particularly for youths (the leaders of tomorrow). John Dewey about a century ago supported and encouraged the ideals in citizenship education because it liberates humans to find freedom and their calling in life (Okam & Ibrahim, 2011). The attainment of these laudable goals, therefore, calls for an examination of Citizenship Education in relation to some coveted values and attitudes that are stipulated in the National Policy on Education such as honesty, integrity, fairness and justice, patriotism, self-discipline, industry, tolerance, obedience and dignity of labour among others.

Integrity stems from the Latin word ‘integer’, which means whole and complete (Benjamin, 2000). It is deduced from this definition that integrity requires an innermost sense of wholeness and regularity of character. As a result of this, people are expected to see integrity in one’s actions, words, decisions, methods and outcomes. It can, therefore, be deduced here that integrity boils down to safeguarding against infringements: making sure that one does not become tarnished or corrupted or that one does not overstep the mark. From a positive perspective when “wholeness” is attached in the definition of integrity. Integrity refers to the implementation of good practices to ensure that one remains whole, in one piece, or unblemished because it is concerned with the values and principles an individual upholds. The conducts of a person of integrity are complete and consistent, that is, the values and principles, actual conduct, and the consequences that are strived for form a coherent whole. The words and deeds of a person of integrity are in conformity with each other. Integrity concerns the degree to which people are integrated, both on a personal level (towards oneself) and in relation to society (towards others).

To support the foregoing, various authors have classified integrity into various types. White (2017) classified integrity into Academic Integrity, Political Integrity and Legal Integrity. In a similar vein, Six and Hubert (2008) classified integrity into Business Integrity, Political Integrity and Personal Integrity. The focus of this study would be Personal Integrity, which is an intrinsic moral persuasion to antagonize things that are not virtuous or morally right; the instinctive tendencies, which persuade individuals to do what they feel and believe is right irrespective of the penalties attached to their resolutions. As a result, people perceived as having high Personal Integrity are usually described as truthful, dedicated, generous, prudent and matured.

Integrity is the feature of being candid and having strong moral principles that are usually exhibited especially on day-to-day living as well as public issues (Yusuf, 2012). This author went further to state that a man of Personal Integrity is one who stands for honesty, accountability, transparency, loyalty, fair play, equity, probity and justice among others and is able to stand by his words and the truth even at the point of death or in the face of threats. Yusuf (2012) informed that students must not only emulate men of integrity in the society but must make it a calling to strive to become one. As such, students of integrity exhibit traits such as moral uprightness, hard-work, diligence, commitment, dedication, avoidance of examination malpractice as well as plagiarism. Thus, students can be considered to be of integrity when they conform and act harmoniously with laid down school rules and regulations even when no one is observing.

Integrity according to Oyekan (2016), is described as the extent to which an individual or group is ethically upright based on absolute and fundamental universal standards. In addition, integrity constituted in real practice should be relative to the social, behavioural and cultural demands and settings of many academic communities as well as the society at large (Oyekan, 2016). Integrity is a concept that needs to be investigated because research findings revealed that there exist some traces of academic dishonesty in the Nigerian educational system (Barnett, 2000; Olasehinde-William, 2006; Olasehinde-Williams & Olawuyi 2011; Orim, 2016). It can, therefore, be deduced that citizenship education is a viable discipline in ensuring integrity because its objectives are derived from the overall objectives of education in Nigeria as derived from the provisions of the Nigerian Constitution. Oyekan (2016) further explained that, to entrench integrity anywhere in Nigeria (academic institutions, religious communities as well as professional spheres) requires key cultural and ethical changes as against what is currently obtainable in the society. These laudable suggestions can be met through Citizenship education because one of its objectives is to transmit cultural values and ethics such as honesty, integrity, commitment, dignity of labour, attitudes and attributes that pose as inevitabilities for societal growth and development to individual students (Umudjere, Okogu, & Osah, 2016).

Furthermore, Fannin (2017), in discussing the concept of integrity, described a person of integrity as the type of person you are in your inner-self when no one is observing as well as the person an individual chooses to portray when hard choices press especially when such choices are not considered moral or morally-inclined. Hence, it is very important for individuals to imbibe and strive to create a sense of integrity in their inner-self, because it makes one better. This means that it is necessary for individuals as well as students in a society to make positive efforts in portraying Personal Integrity characteristics in their daily activities and dealings with their knowledge of Citizenship Education. It therefore becomes imperative that Social Studies students should strive to imbibe a strong spirit of integrity in their dealings both in and out of the school system with their knowledge of Citizenship Education. This is very necessary because, as the leaders and teachers of tomorrow, much is desired and needed from them and as such calls for proper Personal Integrity. This study therefore examined the Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity (PI) and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study was to examine the Comparative relationship between Personal Integrity (PI) and Performance in Citizenship Education among Colleges of Education Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. find out the level of Personal Integrity in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students' in North-central, Nigeria;
2. examine the performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria;
3. Determine the correlation between personal integrity and performance in Citizenship Education among Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What is the level of Personal Integrity in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?
2. What is the mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?
3. Is there any correlation between level of Personal Integrity and mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant correlation between level of Personal Integrity and mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria

Methodology

The research design for this study is the correlational survey research design. Correlational survey research design is suitable for determining whether, and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more variables. The population of the study consists of all NCE Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria during the 2023/2024 academic session. The

study was conducted only in Federal College of Education, Okene, Kogi State; Kwara State College of Education, Oro, Kwara State and Federal College of Education, Kontagora, Niger State. The Integrity Scale and the Citizenship Education Performance Test were instruments used for data collection. The Integrity scale is an 18-item instrument for measuring Personal Integrity. The scale when validated by the developer had reliability coefficient of 0.74. The Scale had a 5-point scaling model ranging 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neither Disagree Nor Agree, 4 = Agree, and 5 = Strongly Agree. The adapted form of the instrument was a 4-point Likert-type scaling model ranging from 1 = SA: Strongly Agreed, 2 = A: Agreed, 3 = D: Disagreed and 4 = SD: Strongly Disagreed requesting respondents to choose the option that best described their opinion of a statement were adopted for clarity of response options. The Citizenship Education Performance Test was used to establish the performance of students in Citizenship Education; their individual score on the 30 test-items were scored and cumulated. The cumulated scores for all the students were converted to percentage such that percentage scores of less than 45 (0- 44) was adjudged Poor, 45-49 as Fair, 50-59 as Good, 60-69 as Very Good and 70-100 as Excellent. The instruments were administered directly to the students with the assistance of lecturers and two trained research assistants on the day approved by the authorities for the exercise. Respondents were assured of the anonymity as well as confidentiality of their responses as no name or any other forms of identity were required. The data collected for this study were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics procedures.

Presentation of Results

Three research questions were raised in this study. Research questions 1 and 2 were answered using frequency scores and percentages while research question 3 that had corresponding null hypothesis was tested using Multiple Regression Analysis. The results are presented below.

Bio-demographic Information of the Students

Table 1: Distribution of Students by Institutions

Institutions	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Federal College of Education Kotangora	244	33.2
Federal College of Education Okene	249	33.9
Kwara State College of Education Oro	242	32.9
Total	735	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the distribution of the Colleges of Education students that participated in this study according to their respective institutions. It showed that out of 735 (100.0%) of the students, 244(33.2%) were selected from the Federal College of Education in Kotangora, 249 (33.9%) from Federal College of Education in Okene while 242 (32.9%) of the students were selected from Kwara State College of Education located at Oro. It is shown in this study that majority of the students that participated in the study were selected from Federal Colleges of Education.

Research Question 1: What is the level of Personal Integrity in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?

The result presented in Table 2 shows the Personal Integrity levels of Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 2: Personal Integrity levels of Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria

Personal Integrity Level	Score Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Low	18 – 36	36	4.9
Moderate	37 – 54	625	85.0
High	55 – 72	74	10.1
Total		735	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2 shows the Personal Integrity levels of Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria. It shows that out of the 735 (100.0%) that participated in this study, 36(4.9%) exhibited a low level of Personal Integrity, 625(85.0%) exhibited a moderate or average level while 74(10.1%) of the Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria exhibited a high level of Personal Integrity. It is indicated from this result that the majority of the Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria had a moderate level of Personal Integrity.

Research Question 2: What is the mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central Nigeria?

The result presented in Table 3 shows the performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria.

Table 3: Performance of Social Studies Students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria

Performance	Score Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Poor	0 – 39	451	61.4
Fair	40 – 49	170	23.1
Good	50 – 59	71	9.7
Very Good	60 – 69	30	4.1
Excellent	70 – 100	13	1.8
Total		735	100.0
Mean score = 36.2			

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3 shows the performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. It shows that out of the 735 (100.0%) that participated in this study, 451(61.4%) had poor performance, 170(23.1%) performed fairly, 71(9.7%) had good performance, 30(4.1%) had very good performance while 13(1.8%) of the students had excellent performance in Citizenship Education. Indication is shown from this result that the performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria is poor.

Hypothesis Testing

H₀: There is no significant correlation between level of Personal Integrity and mean performance score in Citizenship Education among Social Studies Students in North-central, Nigeria

Table 4: Model Summary of multiple regression analysis on relationship among Personal Integrity, Patriotic Attitude and Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig	Decision
Personal Integrity	.327	.107	.104	3.63036	43.732	.000	Reject H₀

Table 4 shows that the relationship among Personal Integrity, Patriotic Attitude and Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. It is indicated from the table that the relationship between Personal Integrity and NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of 0.327 (32.7%) and a multiple correlation square (R²) of 0.107 (10.7%). These values are statistically significant at 0.05 probability level. This implies that Personal Integrity variable accounted for 10.7% of the observed variance in Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education. Therefore, it can be concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between Personal Integrity and NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. Relative contribution of Personal Integrity towards NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education is shown in Table 5.

Table 10: Relative contribution of Personal Integrity to NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.087	1.445		.060	.952
Personal Integrity	.196	.021	.324	9.273	.000

Table 5 shows the relative contribution of Personal Integrity towards Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria. As shown in Table 5, Personal Integrity had beta and t-values of 0.324 and 9.273

respectively. It is therefore shown in this result that Personal Integrity made a significant contribution to NCE Social Studies students' performance in Citizenship Education.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that an average of the Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria had a moderate level of Personal Integrity. This implies that majority of the Social Studies students classified within the moderate level or range in the classification of Personal Integrity. This is in-line with the findings of Benjamin (2017) who reported that the characteristics of Personal Integrity are manifested in capricious permutations and degrees. In addition, it contradicts the findings of Nilsen (2004) and Orim (2006) that evidences of low Personal Integrity are manifested in the Nigerian tertiary education system. This result also negates the findings of Yusuf (2005) and Umudjere, Okogu and Osah (2016) that most Nigerians (NCE students inclusive) are ignorant of their obligations through Personal Integrity as a result of the negative concepts passed-on to them by their ancestors as well as former colonial masters.

This could be attributed to the aftermath of their exposure and interaction to the teaching of tenets of Citizenship Education (SOS 222) as a course of study. Citizenship education as a course of study helps in exposing students to real life experiences that have positive impact on their personality development as well as their interaction in and out of the school system.

The findings of this study revealed that the general performance of Social Studies students in Citizenship Education in North-central, Nigeria was poor. This implies that more than half of the NCE Social Studies students performed below average in the Citizenship Education Performance Test (CEPT). The findings of this study buttress the revelation of Castro (2013), Martins (2008; 2010) and Ozturk, Malkoc and Ersoy (2016) that both pre-service and in-service Social Studies Education teachers have not established and exhibited citizenship education knowledge, understanding and skills at satisfactory levels. In addition, the findings of Merry (2013) revealed that the teaching and learning of citizenship education is currently drifting away from reality that it risks becoming irrelevant due to poor performance of students in the discipline. However, the finding of this study is contrary to the finding of Kerr (2004) in his evaluation that the performance of students in Citizenship Education positively portrays the preparation for their roles and responsibilities as citizens at the preparatory training process. This outcome may be due to the unpreparedness of some of the participants in their role as future classroom teachers who are responsible and expected to teach effectively the content of Civic Education at the Basic School level. It could also be as a result of the nature of the test items (objective test) as against the familiar norm of essay test as means of examination in most of the schools. Another reason for students' poor performance could be attributed to the difference in cultural background of the respondents.

Conclusion

Based on the discussion of the findings, the study concludes that Personal Integrity has significant correlation with performance in Citizenship Education among NCE Social Studies students in North-central, Nigeria. Personal Integrity was also revealed to have a strong significant contribution in the study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Personal integrity should be further promoted generally among students through seminars and workshops, to promote integrity in other facets of the lives of students both in the school and outside.
2. Personal integrity should be promoted through value education workshops and seminars among students.
3. Salient values and attitudes such as personal integrity should be practically demonstrated by teacher-trainers so as to improve the interest of students on the content of Citizenship Education and not just to pass examinations.
4. Social Studies student teachers should make positive efforts towards imbibing acts of Personal Integrity as well as being role models so as to assist them in easily inculcating such and other values into their future learners especially at the Basic school levels.

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